

Economic Empowerment of Pastoralist Fulani Women and Sustainable Development of Nasarawa State, Nigeria

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16846185>

Abstract

Women's empowerment is hindered by discriminatory traditional practices and stereotypes, especially among the culture-bound pastoralist Fulanis across the entire Sahel savannah. In addition to this, low educational status, low access to maternal and reproductive health care services, low access to land and property ownership, early marriage, among others continue to impact on their lived experiences with adverse impact on their pastoralist livelihood in Nasarawa State and Nigeria. This article attempts to assess the impact of economic empowerment and sustainable national development among pastoralist women in Nasarawa State, Nigeria. The study adopts a participatory action research design and a multistage cluster sampling technique to identify the cluster of locations of pastoralists across the 13 Local Government Areas of Nasarawa State, for skills acquisition training organized by Fulbe Development and Cultural Organization (henceforth, FUDECO). Sociocultural approach and social exclusion theory were adopted as theoretical frameworks for the study. Quantitative data were collected and analyzed using frequency and percentages. Findings show that over 70% of the pastoralist women do not have access to education, healthcare, portable drinking water, and land, in addition to high discriminatory practices leading to their low socioeconomic status. The paper recommends that pastoralist women should be allowed to go to school with a strong priority for skills acquisition. Also, efforts should be made to create awareness for the general public on how to embrace pastoralist women as an integral part of the national development framework of Nasarawa State and Nigeria.

Keywords: *Women, Economic Empowerment, Pastoralist, National Development.*

Introduction

Women and children are generally considered the weakest and vulnerable people in any population, making it look like they always need the support and encouragement of men economically, politically, and culturally to perform optimally in society. This necessitated the idea by the Fulbe Development and Cultural Organization (FUDECO) to organize skill acquisition programmes to economically empower pastoralist women in Nasarawa State to generate income and realize their potential. Women's empowerment is generally hindered by discriminatory traditional practices and stereotypes, particularly among the culturally embedded pastoralist Fulanis that cut across the entire Sahel savannah. This is further compounded by their low educational status, low access to maternal and reproductive health care, low access to land and property ownership, early marriages, among others. These factors pose significant constraints to pastoralist women, leading to negative outcomes that undermine their livelihood and, by extension, impede their overall development in Nasarawa State and Nigeria in general.

As the drive to achieve Sustainable Development Goal 5 on gender equality and empowerment of all women and girls by the year 2030 draws nearer (with only 7 years remaining); existing data suggest that a mere 15.4% of Goal 5 indicators are on track, 61.5% are at moderate distance and 23.1 percent are far or very far offtrack from 2030 targets (United Nations-UN, 2023). In many areas of the target, concerns have been raised about the slow progress with emphasis on the fact that at its present rate, it will take an estimated 300 years to end child marriages, 286 years to close gaps in legal protection and remove discriminatory laws, 140 years for women to be represented equally in position of power and leadership in the workplace, and 47 years to achieve equal representation in National parliaments (UN, 2023). Further to this, around 2.4 billion women of working age are not afforded equal economic opportunity and rights as men (UN, 2023).

In 2019, as captured in the United Nations report 2023, one in every five women aged 20-24 years was married before the age of 18, which serves as a basis for women's lack of decision-making power over their sexual and reproductive health and rights. Out of this, 35 percent of women between 15-49 years of age have experienced physical and or sexual intimate partner violence or non-partner sexual violence. One in every three girls has also experienced some form of female genital mutilation and or cutting in 30 countries of Africa and the Middle East.

Gender equality is not only a fundamental human right, but a necessary foundation for a peaceful, prosperous, and sustainable world. As women and girls represent half of the world's population and therefore, half of its potential, but gender inequality persists everywhere and stagnates their social progress. On average, women in the labor market still earn 23 percent less than men globally, and women spend about three times as many hours in unpaid domestic and care work as men. These factors and many others remain a huge barrier to women's empowerment and sustainable development in Nigeria and the global community. This article is an assessment of the impact of women's economic empowerment carried out by the Fulbe Development and Cultural Organization (FUDECO) among pastoralist women in Nasarawa State, Nigeria. FUDECO is a registered non-governmental organization with a humanitarian mandate that is tasked with the primary mission of empowering pastoralist women across the state. So far, it has sponsored the training (skills acquisition) of over 250 pastoralist women in Nasarawa State, focusing on various skills to earn their income with the promise of achieving economic equality.

Literature review and theoretical framework

Women empowerment

The idea of empowerment is an offshoot of the discourse on human development, and it came into prominence after the 1980s. Its linkage with feminist discourse went a long way in shaping the idea of women's empowerment. Empowerment has been defined in different ways depending on its application; 'to infuse people with power' (Narayana, 2002; World Development Report, 2020), that is, access to resources; as expansion in individual's agency (Kishore, 2002), and as power of decision making i.e., autonomy (Jejeebboy, 1995). The concept of

empowerment of women as a goal of development projects and programmes gained wide acceptance in the 1990s. According to Young (2015), the concept of empowerment as used by development agencies, refers mainly to entrepreneurial self-reliance. On the other hand, an empowerment approach to development can also mean public participation in the policy-making and planning processes. Still drawing on Young's (2015) views, it is now recognized in development circles that economic growth and social betterment are best achieved when the mass of the population is informed about and involved in development aims and plans, and sees themselves as a direct beneficiary of the growth in resources that economic expansion should bring. One of the ways to achieve this is structuring the decision-making process to ensure widespread consultation at all levels of society about development goals, the processes by which those goals are to be reached, and the resources needed to achieve them. Empowerment is given to a range of interest groups and NGOs, by using them as consultative bodies or councils.

Sustainable National Development

Sustainable development is a strategic principle that serves as a systematic guide to realize human development goals while also enabling natural systems to provide necessary resources and ecosystem services to humans. The desired result is a society where living conditions and resources meet human needs without undermining the planetary integrity and stability of the natural system. Sustainable development seeks to balance economic development, environmental protection, and social well-being. The Brundtland Report in 1987 defined sustainable development as development that meets the needs of the present generation without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs (Raimi et al., 2015; Raimi, 2015). The concept of sustainable development nowadays has a focus on economic development, social development, and environmental protection for future generations.

Sustainability is a social goal for people to coexist on Earth for a long time. Specific definitions of this term are disputed and have varied across different literary contexts and historical periods. Experts often describe sustainability as having three dimensions (or pillars): environmental, economic, and social, and many publications emphasize the environmental dimension. In everyday use, sustainability often focuses on countering major environmental problems, including climate change, loss of biodiversity, loss of ecosystem services, land degradation, and air and water pollution. The idea of sustainability can guide decisions at the global, national, and individual levels (e.g., sustainable living). A related concept is sustainable development, and the terms are often used interchangeably. UNESCO, as shown in the UN, 2023 report, distinguishes the two by noting that sustainability is often thought of as a long-term goal (i.e., a more sustainable world), while sustainable development refers to the many processes and pathways to achieve it. Sustainable development has the potential of being a groundbreaking concept that can revolutionize the way nations act on a national level, and more on an international level.

In their commitment to the SDGs, Oweibia, Elemuwa, Akpan, Daniel, Oruiko, Tarimobowei, Okoho, Elemuwa, Raimi, and Babatunde (2024) assert that Nigeria has demonstrated strategic foresight by developing the National Economic Recovery and Growth Plan (ERGP). This plan resonates with the SDGs' ethos, outlining key strategies for achieving sustainable and inclusive growth. Furthermore, the establishment of the Ministry of Budget and National Planning symbolizes Nigeria's dedication to overseeing the SDGs' implementation and coordination at a national level (Federal Government of Nigeria, 2017).

On Nigeria's poverty level at the time of adopting the SDGs in 2015, a pivotal year marked by global commitments to reduce poverty and inequality, Nigeria's national poverty rate was alarmingly high. Approximately 40.1% of the population, nearly half of all Nigerians, were living below the national poverty line (Oweibia et al, 2024). Using the 2022 National Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI) report to evaluate poverty across health, education, living standards, and work and shocks reveals that 63% of Nigeria's population resides in poverty. This alarming statistic implies that a substantial 6 out of every 10 Nigerians experience multidimensional poverty, highlighting a significant distance from attaining Goal 1 of the SDGs based on this analysis (Oweibia, 2024). From this, one can easily attest to the effort made by FUDECO on the skills acquisition training as a good attempt to empower the pastoralists to overcome poverty, which, if sustained, could lead to sustainable national development. This is because they are one of the neglected populations where most of these policies and initiatives of the government on poverty eradication do not reach.

Issues in gender equality, women's economic empowerment, and sustainable development

As observed by Murunga (2017), although the rate at which women have been actively involved in community development is on the increase, it is yet to attain its full potential. Some studies carried out in developed countries like the USA, Netherlands, Sweden, and China by the World Bank (2014) and scholars like Chagaka and Rutatora (2016) have shown that development in these countries has been largely met due to the strategic choice of empowering their women. In China, for example, women have equal access to education, information, and technology, enabling them to acquire skills on par with men to participate in the implementation of development projects. Besides, these women have been found to understand the basic problems facing the citizens at the household levels, thus they have been credited for coming up with decisions that guide the project designers and implementers to come up with the best local models of implementing the development projects successfully.

However, in Africa, women are very much disadvantaged in all spheres. For example, women are not allowed to own property like land, women never inherit their parents' properties as compared to men, women have not been given chances to sit in major community development committees and never make major decisions (Laboso, 2014). African Development Bank (2017) has indicated that this is even worse because in some instances where women are allowed to sit in development sittings, their ideas are usually brushed off, and sometimes they are reminded of their roles in cooking and serving the men in these special gatherings. Women have not been given a chance in

Africa as compared to men, despite the fact that they contribute more than men in terms of community resources mobilization, community labor provision, etc. (UN, 2016).

With an estimated population of over 200 million people, Nigeria is easily the most populous country in sub-Saharan Africa and the eighth largest country in the world by population. According to the last census conducted in 2006, Nigerian women were reported to represent about 49.7% of the population. Despite being almost half of the population, this numerical strength of the Nigerian women (most especially women in the north-eastern part) has not affected the age-long inferior status the society bestows on women. Over the years, Nigeria has adopted National policies for the empowerment of women, and the goal of these policies is to bring about the advancement, development, and empowerment of women in the country. However, while progress has been made in this regard, more still needs to be done in terms of entrenching a system that equates women with men in the development trajectory of the country.

In most of the countries in West Africa, women participate in agricultural production more than men. The women farmers undoubtedly remain the key actors in food production in sub-Saharan Africa, a force to be reckoned with in terms of ending hunger, unemployment, and poverty (UN, 2016). In Nigeria, it is very clear that women are actively involved in the production, processing, and marketing of agricultural products. Women have not been given a chance in Africa as compared to men, although they contribute more than men in terms of community resources mobilization, community labor provision, etc. (UN, 2016). Women play a crucial role in agriculture and food supply, contributing significantly to global food security and economic development. They are involved in all stages of the agricultural value chain, from production and processing to marketing and consumption. Their contributions are often undervalued and under-recognized (Gabriela, L.C., 2023). Nevertheless, in farming and marketing, decision-making and policy-making, access to loans, farm inputs, and other agricultural incentives are less considered or favoured. These governmental attitudes show that women are not always empowered for greater productivity in different sectors of the country, such as agriculture, education, and healthcare services, all of which militate against purposeful community development.

Theoretical Framework

This study used the socio-cultural approach as its theoretical orientation. The socio-cultural approach was propounded by Ortneer, Oakley, Bettheim, and Fried (1974). From their perspective, gender roles are the product of culture rather than biology, and as such, culture can be indicted for the present condition of women. This school of thought emerged as a result of the failure of the biological theories to explain the social position of women in society. This approach attempts to locate the differences between males and females within the framework of a culturally defined system.

Ortner et'al (1974) noted at that time that women's status all over the world was that of a second-class citizen. Noting further that the explanation for this is that women are at times identified with something that every culture devalues and or defines as being of a lower order of ranking. She observed further that societies where this happens arrogate gender differential to nature and postulate that this was possible because the reproductive functions of a woman, her social role, and resilient structure place her close to nature rather than culture. Ironically, the more scholars have tried to explain the difference between men and women, the more it becomes clear that the difference is at best tenuous. Usually, what one feels is that the same culture which creates roles and imposes them on sexes is also responsible for widespread beliefs which undermine the role of women.

The socio-cultural viewpoint of women begins with the assumptions that human behavior and conduct are primarily shaped by culture, which is a set of learned behaviors shared by members of a society. As explained in the socio-cultural perspective, the practice of culture and associated beliefs about a particular people and society have been the major drawback for women as regards their participation in developing their communities and also their empowerment. Socio-cultural approach is the best approach to adopt as the theoretical base for this work because it is the culture of the people that places women as weaker vessels, and sees them as less important when decisions need to be taken for the growth of communities, and even in their household. This belief moves from generation to generation. This cultural approach deals with the traditions, beliefs, values, norms, and practices of the people living in the same society.

Methods

The study adopted participatory action research (PAR), which involves Fulbe people directly doing research among their people for the first time to know the root cause of gender equality and its associated problems and proffer solutions for policy intervention and implementation to improve the status of pastoralist women. Convenience sampling was used to select 150 respondents out of the 250 that were trained on skills acquisition across various Fulani settlements in the state. A multistage sampling technique involving the use of purposive sampling, cluster sampling, snowball sampling, and accidental (conducive) sampling was used for the study. The Fulani people were purposively selected for the study, which is in line with the topic under investigation. Hence, the Fulani (Fulbe) settlements, also known as 'Ruga', formed clusters within the study area and were treated as such. Subsequently, the researcher used the snowball sampling technique to reach other settlements after the first. This is a form of sampling where existing study subjects recruit future subjects from among their acquaintances; consequently, the first Fulbe settlement served as a source of further referrals to other settlements for the study. The choice of adopting the snowball technique is because most Fulbe people stay in "ruga" settlements that are on the outskirts of town, and the researcher may experience difficulty in locating them. Through this process, 150 pastoralist women were selected for the study. Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used in processing the data collected

through the questionnaire and analysed using frequency and percentage. Also, qualitative data collected through key informant interviews were analysed thematically and used to complement the quantitative data.

Results and Discussions

Table 1: Socio-demographic Characteristics of Respondents

<i>Characteristics</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent (%)</i>
Sex		
<i>Female</i>	150	100
Total	150	100
Marital status		
<i>Single</i>	37	24.7
<i>Married</i>	101	67.3
<i>Widowed</i>	12	8
Total	150	100
Occupation		
<i>Farmer/pastoralist</i>	44	29.4
<i>Housewife</i>	26	17.3
<i>Small scale business</i>	77	51.3
<i>Others</i>	3	2
Total	150	100
Education		
<i>No formal Education</i>	109	72.7
<i>Primary</i>	8	5.3
<i>Secondary</i>	33	22
Total	150	100

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Findings from Table 1 above indicated 100% respondents were women when asked about their gender, out of which 24.7% are single, 67.3% are married, and 8% are widows. The result further shows that 29.4% of the women are farmers/pastoralists, 51.3% are doing small-scale business, mostly what they were empowered on, and this therefore, signifies how successful the skills acquisition is for the pastoralist women in Nasarawa state. It is a well-known fact that Fulani’s major occupation is pastoralism, but development has forced them to learn other skills in order to fit into today’s reality of life. Again, 17.3% of the respondents are housewives, while 2% others. On the level of education, however, the absolute majority of the respondents, 72.7% do not have formal education, 5.3% attend primary education, while 22% have secondary education in the research area. This is a pointer to the possibilities of gender inequality, even though men were not assessed. However, a low level of education exposes one to a lot of social vices of inequality, poverty, low socioeconomic status, among others.

Table 2: Nature of Gender Equality in the Area

<i>S/N</i>	<i>Impacts</i>	<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Total (%)</i>
1	Do pastoralist women have important roles in your community?	150 (100%)	-	150 (100%)
2	Are women involved in decision making in the area?	122 (81.3%)	28 (18.7%)	150 (100%)

3	Are women allowed to own cattle and livestock?	135 (90%)	15 (10%)	150 (100%)
4	Are women allowed to own property such as houses?	22 (14.7%)	128 (85.3%)	150 (100%)
5	Do women feel respected and valued compared to male members of the family?	8 (5.3%)	142 (94.7%)	150 (100%)

Source: Author’s Fieldwork, 2024

The table above shows the results of the questions asked regarding gender equality in the area. From the result, all the respondents (100%) agree that pastoralist women have important roles in the community. In comparison, 81.3% women concur with the assertion that women are involved in decision making in the area, leaving 18.7% with divergent opinions. 90% respondents, which forms the majority opinion, agree that women are allowed to own cattle and livestock, while 10% disagreed. Conversely, the result revealed that the majority of the respondents opined that women are not allowed to own property such as houses, an indicator of the patriarchal nature of the society. Lastly, on whether women feel respected and valued compared to male members of the family, 5.3% agreed while 94.7% disagreed. These findings imply that, although women have salient roles to play in society, a wide gender gap still exists between men and women in terms of how women are treated compared to their male counterparts. This is in tandem with the assertion that most Nigerian communities are patriarchal, where there is male dominance and gender inequality. This highlights the need for more effort and indices to be put in place to bridge the wide gender gap between men and women in society.

Table 3: Respondents’ views on Skill Acquisition Services

S/N	Questions	Yes	No	Total (%)
1	Have you been trained by FUDECO?	100%	--	100
2	Did you receive training on how to make shoes and bags?	6.3%	93.7%	100
3	Were you taught how to make soap, detergent, izal and shampoo?	87%	13%	100
4	were hair dressing and making small chops among the skills taught?	65%	35%	100

Source: Author’s Fieldwork, 2024

The results also shows that 100% of the targeted pastoralist were trained by FUDECO on the skills acquisition in various parts of the state on shoes and bags making with 6.3%, on soap, detergent, Izal, Shampoo, Omo etc. 43.7% and a host of others on groundnut cake, hairstyle, Lalle, puff-puff, Palm oil with over 65% and up to now this serves as their major source of income/businesses as vindicated by them and were proud of FUDECO’s intervention and even requested when asked on whether FUDECO should continue with the training or not, all of them encourage FUDECO to continue with the skills acquisition as this is the first time they were involve in decision making and impacted with the skills to enhanced their living conditions as empowerment.

One of the beneficiaries of the empowerment narrates her story as:

I am from Kokona Local Government living in Garaku and I was part of the persons who received FUDECO’s skills acquisition training on Poultry farming sometimes last three years and was awarded with certificate in addition to the take-off grants to continue with the business, and am proud that today I have over 50 birds under my care. I do earn between #50,000 to #100,000 naira

at the end of every two to three months after selling/disposing off all the birds I reared then buy some new one's again. I am deeply happy over the gesture by the FUDECO, IDRC-SPARC, Co-water and its official and AYNI foundation for supporting us to generate personal income (Female Interviewee, Aged 47 years, Garaku, 2024).

Another beneficiary of the skills acquisition programme added that;

I received a training on Poultry farming and awarded with a certificate in Nasarawa State University Keffi sometime last three years and I was given a token to start practicing what I learned and this has yielded positive results on my part because I can stand on my own with the little income am currently generating at the end of every stock. I thank FUDECO, AYNI Foundation, Co-water and all other NGOs who supported us in one way or the other towards impacting positively on our lives. I paid and support my husband and my children in their schooling and other domestic chores since my purchasing power has improved. I want to further inform you that I have over 30 birds in my possession with the capital given to me. Thank you, thank you and thank you (Female Interviewee, Age 54 years, Garaku, 2024).

While some were trained on Poultry farming, others were trained on other skill areas such as weaving, palm oils, yoghurt, donuts, shoes and bags, detergent (liquid soap, bathing soap, Omo, Izal, etc), room fresher, rub, perfumes, and a host of others. This is corroborated by another respondent who stated that:

I am from Wamba Local Government who was once trained by FUDECO on Palm product as empowerment to enable me generate income to support myself and my family. Today, I want to assure you that I produce palm oil at the comfort of my house and earn income without going outside of my residence and I am also proud to tell you that I am even training other people on same skills in addition to my children. This has helped me a lot in generating daily income to support my children and relatives (Female Interviewee, Age 60 years, Wamba, 2024).

Additionally, one of the participants who benefitted from the skills acquisition training on Palm oil and palm kernel, soap making and groundnut cake in Wamba Local Government with a lot of success story. I normally produce palm oil from the raw palm oil, which I normally buy at N10,000 to get three gallons, and to be sold at N6,000 and or N7,000, depending on the market price, and make a profit of at least N8,000 or N10,000. I do this 3-4 times monthly and when you multiply N6,000 by 3 will give N18,000 or there about and this continues. Thank you FUDECO, AYNI foundation, SPARC-IDRC and anyone who has effort in making this a reality to us (Female Interviewee, Aged 38 years, Wamba 2024)

Another respondent trained by FUDECO, considered to be one of the most dedicated beneficiaries of the programme, given the visible growth of her business, expressed the view that;

I am into detergent (perfumes, liquid soap, room freshener, Vaseline etc) and I am proud that I make a lot of profit of over 150,000 naira and also diversify into farming and today the business has grown to making daily profit of an average of N10,000 on weekly basis. I trained other women on this type of business and I want to categorically tell you that I have financial independent since

my children and any other person close to me is benefitting from the skills I learned through FUDECO. May almighty Allah continue to support fudeco and its official in rendering services to humanity (Female Interviewee, Ages 61 years, Wamba LG, 2024).

In fact, FUDECO’s officials in Nasarawa and National level identified this beneficiary as the most serious among the pastoralist women trained by FUDECO and this a lone is a key achievement associated with FUDECO programmes on women economic empowerment in Nasarawa State, Nigeria. This shows the impact of this empowerment on women generally and in extension gender equality since economic empowerment has been considered to be a strong indicator of gender equality globally.

Table 4: Respondents’ feelings on the training, certificate received and the award ceremony

S/N	Questions	*VH	*H	*N	U	VU
1	Are you happy because you have something doing unlike before?	122 (81.3%)	28 (18.7%)	-	-	-
2	How does learning a skill and earning a living independently makes you feel?	120 (80%)	21 (19.3%)	9 (6%)	-	-
3	How do you feel with the programme from FUDECO?	11 (7.3%)	139 (92.7%)	-	-	-
4	How did your family, friends and relative feel when you received the training and started income generation activities?	75 (50%)	57 (37.5%)	18 (12.5%)	-	-

* VH= Very Happy; H= Happy; N= Neutral; U= Unhappy; VU= Very Unhappy
(Source: Fieldwork, 2024)

The findings also go down to ask about their feelings on the training, certificate received and the award ceremony and with all forms of nostalgia the responses were positive with 62.5% being happy because they have something doing unlike before that they were redundant, 30% very happy because they learned skills and earning a living independent of their own and only 7.5% remain neutral on the scaling made. With over 92% happy and having a technical skill that made them stand on their own is a serious achievement when such a programme is to be evaluated, and this signifies that equality to some extent, since a pastoralist woman will not wake up in the morning and request for everything from her husband, marking her 100% dependency. If this is sustained soon, gender equality among pastoralists is non-negotiable

Justifying the above, responses on how family, friends, and relatives treated pastoralist women who received the training and started income generation activities show that 50% of the respondents were treated well, valued, and respected by the family members, 37.5% were treated very well. In comparison, 12.5% indicated that they were treated as usual. This finding justifies the fact that family members have a change in their attitude in terms of treatment with those generating personal income having a special position or status in the family, unlike before, and is in consonance with the saying that what a man can do, a woman can also do it better. Some even indicate that

they are now teaching some of their relatives what they learn from FUDECO’s skills acquisition and therefore serve as a change in the mentality of the pastoralist women.

Table 5: Impacts of the pastoralist women empowerment initiatives carried out in the past few years in Nigeria

<i>S/N</i>	<i>Impacts</i>	<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Total (%)</i>
1	Have the empowerment programmes increased your standard of living?	150 (100%)	-	100
2	Do you earn money from the skill you acquired?	150 (100%)	-	100
3	Has the skill acquisition helped you in saving and investment?	150 (100%)	-	100
4	Has the women empowerment programme helped you to take care of your family?			

Source: Author’s Fieldwork, 2024

The result shows that the empowerment programmes organized by FUDECO have positively affected the lives of people in the study area. This is because all the respondents (100%) agree that the empowerment programmes increased their standard of living. After all, they can now earn enough money from it and can even save and invest money. This is one of the giant strides towards becoming self-sufficient, especially in patriarchal societies where women are mostly dependent on men for survival.

Findings

Findings from the study show that all respondents for the study are females, this is because the study is on women's pastoralist empowerment and gender equality based on what the pastoralists view as equality. The result further shows that 29.4% of the women are farmers/pastoralists, 51.3% are doing small-scale business, mostly what they were empowered on, and this therefore, signifies how successful the skills acquisition is for the pastoralist women in Nasarawa state. It is a well-known fact that Fulani’s major occupation is pastoralism, but development has forced them to learn other skills in order to fit into today’s reality of life. Again, 17.3% of the respondents are housewives, while 2% others. On the level of education, however, the absolute majority of the respondents, 72.7% do not have formal education, 5.3% attend primary education, while 22% have secondary education in the research area. With the majority of the respondents not being educated, the ground for inequality has already been established and thus further pushes women to the bottom. This is corroborated by Ortner et al.’s (1974) study, which observed that women’s status all over the world is that of a second-class citizen. Therefore, lack of education serves as a root cause of inequality. With this type of skills acquisition by NGO’s and other government agencies, if sustained, may lead to the changing culture of women's second-class status and as such inequality may become a thing of the past.

On skills acquisition, however, all the targeted respondents were trained on one form of skills or the other, which gave them ground to stand on, aside from pastoralism as their way of life opened another window of opportunities

to earn a living outside traditional business as such, they were well equipped to live a better life because of the empowerment. Studies carried out in developed countries like the USA, Netherlands, Sweden, and China by the World Bank (2014) and scholars like Chagaka and Rutatora (2016) have shown that development in these countries has been largely met due to the strategic choice of empowering their women. This was demonstrated by the follow-up in-depth interviews conducted, whereby the majority of the beneficiaries indicated that they had been empowered, and were happy and even respected by their husbands and relatives, since they can generate income of their own, which is used to support their families and even sponsored their children's education. If this type of programme were to be sustained, the farmers/herders crisis, gender inequality, and poverty will soon become history in Nasarawa State and Nigeria in extension.

Conclusion

The study was necessary because growing concerns about the impacts of women's empowerment on sustainable development have generated lots of interest as to enhancing the political and economic capacity of the local women in developing countries like Nigeria, where vulnerability to low political and economic capacity is high. After all, they are the marginalized group in the society (Ihemeje, 2013; Agbalajobi, 2010). Thus, women's empowerment is a vehicle for ensuring effective sustainable development. In light of these discoveries that reveal the zeal, courage, strength, and constraints of women toward sustainable development in society, it thus appears that women contribute so much but achieve a little due to their level of empowerment, which is ridiculously low. This shows that women are essential to poverty reduction because of their role in increasing economic opportunities; thus, women are the cornerstone of development. Corroboratively, women are increasing behind the organization of co-operatives producing artisan goods as well as agricultural products from food crops to cash crops in the quest to enhance their livelihoods, their communities, and national development.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are made;

- i. There should be prioritization and provision of sound education, both formal and informal, for women of all ages in the society. This is because sound education will equip girls and women in communities with the skills they need to develop themselves and the society at large. Education and training should be given to women in the local government areas irrespective of their age. Through this medium, more local government women would be sensitized about their rights, roles, and responsibilities toward the development of their localities and thereby catalyze the sustainable development process nationally, which may lead to a change in the culture of women's second-class status.

- ii. Also, efforts should be made to strengthen women at the local government level in Nigeria. This is because when citizens at the local government level do not enjoy public essential services such as good road networks, electricity supply, potable water, functioning health centres, and free education, they are less likely to contribute to their locality. Specifically, the local government shall offer the Nigerian women at that level the environment and avenue to articulate, develop, and achieve their potentials. At the same time, their role and contributions to sustainable development constitute an integral part of the development process, thus stressing the need for these indices to be accessible to them.
- iii. Sequel to this, local government can achieve economic development by empowering women in the following ways: expansion of employment opportunities for women, establishment of functional training and skill acquisition centers for women living in the rural areas and the provision of health facilities which are readily available and accessible in order to boost maternal health, thus reducing the rate of maternal mortality.

Funding

This work was carried out by FUDECO with the aid of a grant from Canada's International Development Research Centre (IDRC), awarded in partnership with the Supporting Pastoralism and Agriculture in Recurrent and Protracted Crisis (SPARC) Programme, which is funded by the United Kingdom's Foreign, Commonwealth and Development Office (FCDO). Opinions stated are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the policies or opinions of IDRC, FCDO, or partners.

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